

Contemporary Issues and Trends in Training and Development

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Abstract

For the company productivity training assumes great significance. Though it is a type of education, training is job oriented. Learning has a greater importance for the success of modern industry. Education plays a very important role in budding and increases these competencies. Change of technology demands that employees update their knowledge, skills, abilities and technical expertise. Jobs are becoming more interdependent tough high interpersonal and crisis solving skill, which can be acquired only through training. Training is a continuous and perennial activity. Training assists the persons in selecting, using and calculating the experiences. It ensures the quick grabbing of knowledge, continued, right kind of inputs are acquired, assembled and integrated in the personality. Improvement provides knowledge and understanding to individuals which enable them for the purpose of more effective work in the industry through problem-solving, inter-personal relation and decision-making.

Keywords: Training, education, personality, job oriented, learning, development.

Introduction

Learning and improvement is a subsystem of an company, the organisation ensures that randomness is reduced and learning or behavioural change takes place in an organized format. Training and development programmes are organised towards maintaining and improving current job performance, while development programmers seek to develop skills for future jobs. Learning programme is a process planned to preserve or get better present occupation recital the management development programme is process designed to develop skills necessary for future work activities. Training and development is a process of task concerned with organizational action intended at bettering the job performance of individuals and groups in managerial settings. Training and development can be described “an enlightening course which involves the sharpening of skills, concepts, changing of attitude and gaining more knowledge to enhance the performance of employees”. The field is known by several names, including “human resources development”, “human capital development” and “learning and development”.

Training is a sub-system of human resource development. The human resource development function cannot be discharged effectively unless comprehensive data on various HR functions including training is available. In order to make trainees interest in competency and skill the HR function should create effective environment wherein good performance is rewarded and poor performance will be punished. It can be achievable by measures like winning completion of training with confirmation of placement, promotion, placement and institutalized a system of rewards for competence and performance. Training and development is very important role in human resource development. It is assumed to be an important role in awaken of the advancement of technology which has resulted in yet growing competition, increase in customer’s expectation of quality and service and a subsequent need to lower costs. It has become a more important globally in order to prepare workers for new jobs.

Definition of Training And Development

Randall S.Schuler in his book effective personnel management defines training and development as “any effort to improve present or potential member of staff presentation by rising an employee’s skill to carry out through knowledge, usually altering the employee’s approach or escalating his or her skill and knowledge. The need for training and development is determined by the employee’s concert insufficiency and is computed as follows:

Training And Development need= Standard performance –Actual Performance

Training And Development as considered learning experiences deliberate to provide workers with the competencies required to execute their in progress or prospect jobs.

Objectives of Training And Development

The principal of Training And Development division is to make sure the availability of a skilled and willing workfare to an organization. There are four other objectives:

- Individual
- Organizational
- Functional
- Societal

Managers can use four measures to conclude the training desires of individuals in their organization or sub component

1. Piece Appraisal: each employee’s work is calculated against the performance standards or objectives established for his or her job.
2. Psychoanalysis of career Requirement: the skills or knowledge specified in the appropriate job description are examined and those employees without necessary skills or knowledge become candidates for training programme.
3. Managerial Analysis: the effectiveness of institute and its success in meeting its goals are analyzed to determine where difference exist
4. Employee Survey: Managers and non-managers are asked to describe what problems are being knowledgeable in their work and what actions they believe are necessary to resolve.

Difference between Training and Development

	Training	Development
1	Training focuses on technical, mechanical oriented operations	It focuses on theoretical skill and conceptual ideas
2	meant for operatives	meant for executives
3	It is short term process	It is continuous process
4	focuses on present need of an employee	focuses on future need of an employee
5	enterprise is taken by the management	program is taken by an individual.
6	Concerned with specific job skills and behavior	Here it is concerned with related enhancement of general knowledge and understanding of non-technical organization function
7	It is for non-managers	It is for managers and executives
8	Meant for job-oriented process and is vocational in nature.	Expansion is general in nature strives to inculcate initiative, creativity, dedication loyalty amongst executives.
9	Motivation is extrinsic	Motivation is intrinsic
10	Assessment for training is considered to be essential	No assessment for development

Significance of Training and Development

For companies to keep improving, it is essential for organizations to have continuous training and development programs for their employees. Competition and the business environment keeps changing, and hence it is critical to keep learning and pick up new skills. The importance of training and development is as follows:

- Best utilization of Human resources
- Development of skills
- To increase the production
- To provide the zeal of team spirit
- For improvement of association culture
- To improve quality, safety
- To increase profitability
- Improve the morale and corporate image

Need for Training and Development

Training and development of employees is a costly activity as it requires a batch quality inputs from trainers as well as employees. But it is essential that the company revises its goals and efficiencies with the changing environment. Here are a few critical reasons why the company endorses training and development sessions.

- When management thinks that there is a need to improve the performances of employees
- To set up the benchmark of improvement so far in the performance improvement effort
- To train about the specific job responsibility
- To test the new methodology for increasing the productivity

Advantages of training and development

Training and development have a cost attached to it. However, since it is beneficial for companies within the long run, they ensure employees are skilled regularly. Some advantages are:

1. Helps employees develop new skills and increases their knowledge.
2. Improves efficiency and productivity of the individuals as well as the team member.

3. Proper training and development can remove bottle-necks in operations.
4. New & improved job positions can be created to make the group leaner.
5. Keeps employees motivated and refresh their goals, ambitions and contribution levels.

Disadvantages of Training and Development

Even though there are several advantages, some drawbacks of training and development are as given below:

1. It is an expensive process which includes arranging the correct trainers and engaging employees for non-revenue activities.
2. There is a risk that after the training and development session, the employee can quit the job.

Training and Development Process

Training and development is a continuous process as the skills, knowledge and quality of work needs constant improvement. Since businesses are changing rapidly, it is critical that companies focus on training their employees after constantly monitoring them & developing their overall personality.

Steps for training and development processes are

1. Determine the need for training and development for individuals or teams
2. Establish specific objectives & goals which needs to be achieve
3. Select the methods of preparation
4. Conduct and implement the programs for employees
5. Evaluate the output and performance post the training and development sessions.
6. Keep monitor and evaluate the performance and formerly see more training if required.

The following are the key factors in designing and development of training programmed:

1. The learner
2. The facilitator or the trainer
3. The learning environment
4. Learning characteristics
5. Training resources and training policies

1) The learner: The learner occupies the centre stage. The learner environment, age, past knowledge, prior learning and educational level of the learners- are all imperative. While scheming the programme we may start with an inventory and discussion of learning style. It will facilitate the instructor to have a feel of selecting the method of training. This may facilitate adult learning method like experiential problem-solving approach to learning.

2) The catalyst or the trainer: whatever the learner wants to learn, it is facilitated by the trainer. This means the trainer should have something significant to pass on besides acceptable personality and effective communication. The level of trainer’s skill, knowledge and ease with which he could approve himself to the different methods of teaching.

3) The learning environment: The learning environment in particular means physical environment. The design should take into consideration the physical location of instruction when he wants to explain, the fuel tank manufacturing two-wheeler factory. He has to certainly take into account the noise level prevailing in that place. For such clarification the design may consider vestibule training to make learning effective.

4) Learning characteristics: learning characteristics like motivation, individual difference, level of learning, interference while learning to the real work area, etc. play a significant role in their

application to the design of training. The learning characteristics are motivation knowledge of result, feedback, trial and error, size of learning, individual differences, era of learning, structure of knowledge, interference and transfer of work etc.

5) Training resources and training policies: The resource allocation is one of the main, critical aspects of guidance system. A realistic rate of benefit analysis will throw true light on benefits of training, role of training in meeting needs and its credibility. The benefits of schooling must outweigh costs. A professional approach to training will not burden the resources. However, issues like top management commitment, budget availability and organizational culture provide either opportunity or threat for training initiatives.

Training and Development Trends in an Industry

1. The definition of “leader” is broadening. A majority of employees in a society now consider individuals to be manager based on their impact, not on their authority or position. organizer is viewed whether they manage others or not, who is peak performer in their specific role.
2. More organization avoids the term “high potential”. Because of their growing lack of enthusiasm to call candidates for accelerated career development “high potential” the word may suggest that other employees do not have much potential, which is not a healthy message to convey, either to the employees or to the institute.
3. More and extra employees now seek entry into management programs.
4. Emergent focus is on developing individual contributors.
5. Management faces a more risk-averse workforce.

Issues Faced By Training and Development

1. Dealing with changes in business
2. Developing leaders
3. Engaging learners
4. Delivering consistent training
5. Conflict management
6. Tracking and post Assessment
7. Adapting exercise to millennial

Conclusion

Training and Development programs are imperative for a club to develop the employee Training aims at continued self-development of the employees. Employees are expected to build up themselves continuously in the union. Working out and expansion helps the growth of a industry. The company needs to have motivated and confident staff who have up-to-date skills in arrangement to remain aggressive.

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